

To Assess the Knowledge on Management of Urinary Incontinence Among Older Women in Kelejora Community Area at Asansol, West Bengal

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Abstract

Introduction

The world's population is aging rapidly, in 2020; the number of people aged 60 years and older was 1.4 Billion. By 2050, the people aged 60 years and older will 2.1 billion. Urinary incontinence is a incontinence leakage of urine. Urinary incontinence is a common condition in the general population, especially the older adults. Urinary incontinence is one of the important geriatric problems whose prevalence has been increasing with ageing. It twice as common in women as in men and affects at least 1 in 3 older women.

Material and methods: Cross sectional descriptive study was conducted among 100 older women selected by purposive sampling techniques to assess the knowledge on urinary incontinence in Kelejora community areas at Asansol.

Results: The level of knowledge about UI, 87% of the older women have inadequate knowledge and the knowledge mean score was 6.48 ± 2.01 . There is an association was found between level of knowledge of UI with age in years, marital status and comorbidity.

1. Introduction

WHO - Older women refers to women age 55 and older. The world's population is aging rapidly, in 2020, the number of people aged 60 years and older was 1.4 Billion. By 2050, the people aged 60 years and older will 2.1 billion.

According to the International Association of Urinary Incontinence (ICS), any involuntary leakage of urine is called urinary incontinence (UI). Urinary incontinence has been identified as a health priority by the World Health Organization. Urinary incontinence is a common condition in the general population, especially the older adults, whose prevalence has been increasing with ageing.. It twice as common in women as in men and affects at least 1 in 3 older women. Urinary incontinence, which is two to three times higher among older women than older men.

Urinary incontinence is divided into 3 main classifications. 1. Stress Urinary incontinence refers to the leakage of urine due to the increased intraabdominal pressure during the incidence such as cough, sneezing, laughing or doing some activities like exercise, lifting frequently triggers. 2. Urge Urinary incontinence is a sudden and intense urge to urinate and leakage of urine at the same time or shortly after due to involuntary contraction of the bladder, which gives sensations of urgency and frequency. 3. Mixed Urinary incontinence is a combination of SUI & UUI, its more common among older women for example , SUI,UUI often occur simultaneously in women, this can sometimes difficult to identify the particular types.

The significant potential risk factors for UI includes increasing age, numbers of parity, obesity, surgeries, chronic constipation and chronic respiratory problems.

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Urinary incontinences has many physical, mental and social effects in older women such as physical issues includes pressure ulcer, decreased sleep quality, UTI, falls and fractures. Common mental problems in these people includes depression, anxiety, therefore among older adults may develop social problems such as social isolation, decreased daily activities in work, travel, physical exercises, sexual dysfunction and thus reduces the quality of life.

Need for the study:

According the urology foundation care key statistics shows that about 1 in 3 women suffers from urinary incontinences. About 1 out of 3 of women age 60 and about half (1 OUT OF 2) women age 65 years and above

Various studies of prevalence of UI in India show ranges from 10% in rural areas and 34 % in urban areas. Brijit Biwas 2023 study reported that 27.7% women were found having UI in Kolkata. Vinal Charpot 2022, study result revealed that the prevalence of UI was 29.36, in particularly 51.70% of young females found stress UI followed by 37.15% in mixed UI and 11.15% in urge UI. The range of reported in international studies show an overall prevalence of UI among young men in 3% - 5% and 11% to 34% in elderly women. Liby Baby 2018 conducted a descriptive survey design among 842 Middle aged women (35-65yrs) selected by purposive sampling techniques. Out of 842 middle aged women, maximum of 609(72.3%) are having either one or more than one symptoms of stress urinary incontinence or 233(27.7%) are not having any symptoms of stress urinary incontinence. Elderly patients generally suffer incontinences thinking it is normal to have a leak but inconstancies are not a natural phenomenon. However due to little awareness, the impact on the quality of life is huge.

India, women generally do not reveal the symptom of urinary incontinence due to culture pressure. Health-seeking behavior is low in India, especially for urinary incontinence, and quality of life is very low due to low levels of awareness, embarrassment, financial problems and fear associated with treatment.

The researcher reasons to carry the research there is a need for more knowledge about the management of

options for the main health conditions that affect them especially urinary incontinence.

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the knowledge on management of urinary incontinence among older women in Kelejora community area at Asansol, West Bengal
2. To find the association between level of knowledge of urinary incontinence with demographic variables among older women in selected in Kelejora community area at Asansol, West Bengal

Hypothesis

H₁: There is an association between level of knowledge with selected demographic variables.

2. Methodology

- Research Approach: Quantitative Research Approach was used.
- Research Design: Descriptive Cross Sectional Study design was selected for the present study.
- Setting: Kelejora Community area in Asansol, West Bengal
- Population: Older women in Asansol, West Bengal
- Sample: Older women in Kelejora community area
- Sample Size: 100 Older women, calculated sample size with the reference of previous studies prevalence of urinary incontinence was 26.47% conducted by (Aathira Kizhakkeveetil Ajith, et.al in 2019
- Sampling Technique: Non Probability Purposive Sampling Technique method
- Sample Selection Criteria:
 - Inclusion Criteria
 - a. Older women in the Age group of 55 years and above
 - Exclusion Criteria
 - a. Older women with mentally disorders
 - b. Older women not willing to participate
- Ethical permission: Approval was obtained from the institutional ethics committees and formal approval was taken from the Panchayat in kelejora community area. The purpose of the study was explained to the older women and an

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informed consent was procured and given surety to be maintaining privacy and confidentiality.

- The Description of the tool 2 sections.
 - Section: 1 - Consists of demographic variables such as age in years, marital status, educational level, occupational status; older women stay with, complaints of urinary incontinences, comorbidity.
 - Section: 2 - Consist of 20 items of structured knowledge questionnaire includes meaning, causes and signs and symptoms, management to find the knowledge on urinary incontinences
- After data collection from the older women, researcher have distributed the information booklet on management of urinary incontinence

3. Result:

The study finding are analysed and interpreted with following headings

Section – A – Result of Demographic Variables among Older women

- According to the demographic variables, 59% were in the age group of 55 to 60 years, 23% were in the age group of 61 – 65 years, 18% were in the age group of 66 and above.
- In the educational level, 62% of the older women have no formal education and 34% have primary and secondary education, 4% are in higher education with a degree and above.
- 79% of older women are married and 21% are widowed.
- In occupational status, 51% of older women are daily wages earners, 24% are house wife and 25% work in the government and private sector.
- Among older women, 72% live with a husband and children, 15% with married children's. 13% live alone.
- According the comorbidity, 69% older women suffered from hypertension, diabetic mellitus and and 31% older women not affected with chronic diseases.

Section – B- Level of knowledge, mean and standard deviation

Table: 1- Level of Knowledge, Mean and Standard Deviation

Level of knowledge	F	%	Mean / Standard deviation
Inadequate knowledge	87	87	6.48 ± 2.01
Moderate knowledge	9	9	
Inadequate knowledge	4	4	

According to the distribution of the level of knowledge about urinary incontinences, 87% of the older women have inadequate knowledge, 9% have moderate knowledge and 4% have adequate knowledge. Among older women the mean knowledge score of mean and standard deviation is 6.48±2.01.

Sections – C – Find the association between level of knowledge with Demographic Variables.

A significant association was found between age in years, complaints of urinary incontinences and comorbidly.

Hypothesis testing

H₁: The association was found with the age in years (p value-0.02), complaints of urinary incontinence (p value- 0.02) and co- morbidly (p value – 0.04) is partially accepted for significant association with selected demographic variables at 0.05 level of significant.

4. Discussion

The results of the present study revealed that urinary incontinences is a common condition among older women with the effect of physical, mental, social and sexual on everyday life. Our study was to find the knowledge on management of urinary incontinence.

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Objective: 1 - To assess the knowledge on management of urinary incontinence among older women in selected setting at Asansol.

The result of the present study showed that, there was inadequate knowledge about UI i.e. among 100 older women 87 older women had inadequate knowledge.

This study was supported by BS suchithraet.al.(2020) conducted on enhancing knowledge on urinary incontinence – A pre and post interventional study result showed that 53(88%) women had poor knowledge, 7 (12%) had average knowledge regarding UI

Objectives: 2- To find the association between level of knowledge of urinary incontinence with demographic variables among older women

The result of present study revealed that, a significant association was found between age in years, complaints of urinary incontinences and co-morbidly.

This study was supported by Sultan Z Alshehri(2022) conducted study in patterns of urinary incontinence among women, the result showed that a significant association was found between age in years, marital status and associated co-morbidity.

Limitations

- The study was limited to 100 older women
- Older women were selected in particular community area

Conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest to conduct this study.

Source funding: Self

5. Conclusion:

Urinary incontinence is a common problem among women and is associated with increasing age. The result of present study found that 87% participants in the study had inadequate knowledge about UI. Urinary incontinence is a condition that can be diagnosed and managed at an early stage. Future research should focus on preventive strategies, such as

pelvic floor muscle exercise and bladder training programs, to play an important role in improving public health with an increasingly ageing population.

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